

THE HYBRID CHARACTER OF COLOUR REVOLUTIONS

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Abstract

According to their characteristics, it can be said that colour revolutions are a kind of "hybrid", i.e. a combination of a coup d'état and a classical revolution. That is, as in the case of a coup d'état, there is a change in the holder of supreme power, without broader social changes (without changes to the state system and the economic and political system), with a certain role of the national army and other security bodies (this time more passive), as well as with support from an external factor. The similarity with classical revolutions, apart from the name, is also represented by the significant role of the masses in the realization of this type of coup. The term "revolution" is used because it evokes positive feelings and expectations of progressive change. As in other types of coups, a large number of actors in colour revolutions, primarily protesters in the streets, are not fully aware of their true role and the events that are taking place. Without taking all this into account, they are used as evidence of mass anti-government sentiment, and if necessary, in the event of intervention by government security forces, they can also serve as a living wall and protection for the real bearers and leaders of the movement.

Keywords: hybrid threats, colour revolutions, security situation.

Introduction

In the 21st century, states cope well with security threats from other states. Even when there was an interstate war in which there was a large difference in the balance of power, such as Iraq's invasion of Kuwait, the international community, with joint forces, prevented such behaviour of states. However, another type of war has become relevant in the 21st century, and these are hybrid wars, which have shown the unwillingness of international bodies to identify and deal with them. Therefore, we can freely say that a global recognition and rearrangement is underway, characterized by conflict between the leading actors on the political, religious or social scene.

Hybrid wars are not characteristic only of the strongest, they are also used by other countries, primarily those that fight to maintain the status of regional powers, and are even used by non-state organizations, such as ISIS, to achieve their own goals.

Hybrid war

The efforts to give a clear seal and recognition of phenomena and processes in social relations, especially as our interest in the sphere of security requires us to consider the emerging forms, methods, means and modalities of the relatively new concept of hybrid war from several aspects. However, the concept of hybrid warfare is not new, as

states and intelligence services have used emerging forms, methods, means and modalities of hybrid action in the past, especially expressed through subversive techniques and tools, to achieve their goals. The KGB used disinformation and propaganda as a means of asymmetric warfare in the Cold War due to the large borders of its population and the regions that were under its sphere of influence, just as the CIA used them to prevent the spread of communism in the United States and Western countries⁹⁵.

With the development of technology, hybrid warfare takes on a completely new dimension, where the overall space could be manipulated by using various "weapons" in the form of an unnoticeable, but persistent and purposeful action in the direction of weakening the supporting elements of a social community. Hybrid warfare, by combining conventional military techniques and unconventional technologies with conventional methods, has become the leading generation of tools that the world is slowly facing⁹⁶. If there is no use of conventional weapons, then there is no war. Everything can be reduced to conflict, to clash and ultimately to war. So, conflict does not always have to lead to clash, and clash does not always have to cause war, but war is always a consequence of the existence of conflicts and clashes.

The remarkable growth of hybrid wars in the 21st century does not mean the end of classic, conventional wars, which we are particularly witnessing with the war between Russia and Ukraine. However, the increasing role of hybrid wars in achieving the geopolitical goals of the opposing sides means that a different approach is needed when creating the defence strategy of the states that are the target of this type of war.

In hybrid warfare, the role of non-military means of a subversive nature is emphasized. Ideally, the state that plans and carries out the "attack" should not use military force and conventional weapons. The goal of the attackers is to control the actions of the political leadership and population of the attacked state and direct them in the desired direction for them, a direction contrary to the determinations of the state⁹⁷. If military force is used, it is used secretly, covertly, with a good alibi. However, although the role of the use of non-military means is particularly emphasized, according to many authors, both in classical wars and in hybrid wars, the basis is the armed conflict as a last resort.

As a working definition in the paper, this will be used: hybrid war as an armed conflict that is carried out in combination with military and non-military means in order to force the enemy to take such steps that he would not do voluntarily, with their synergistic effect, and where at least one party to the conflict is a state. The main role in achieving the goals of the operations is the use of non-military means, such as psychological and propaganda operations, economic sanctions, embargoes, criminal activities, terrorist activities and other subversive activities of a similar nature. As secondary are the military actions of the aggressor, which are carried out in secret, with irregular forces, in combination with symmetrical and asymmetrical methods of combat operations against the entire society and especially against its political structures, state bodies and local self-government, the state economy, the morale of the population, and against the armed forces.

⁹⁵ Davor M. Milošević, Pojmovno određenje fenomena hibridnog ratovanja, *Војно Дело*, 3/2018, стр. 301.

⁹⁶ *Ibid*, str.303

⁹⁷ Hybrid warfare: A new phenomenon in Europe's security environment, Jagello 2000 for NATO Information Centre in Prague, 2015.

The basis of the concept of hybrid war is found in subversion⁹⁸. Thus, according to the above, it can be seen that armed struggle is the essence of war, by quite explicitly emphasizing its reduced role in relation to the other elements of war. It is considered that hybrid war is essentially the achievement of set goals with little or no direct fighting⁹⁹. Therefore, in hybrid wars it is almost impossible to say when the real fight or organized violence begins, which is actually war, conflict, in its classic form. One of the key ideas of hybrid wars is that the difference between the separate categories of war and peace, as well as civilian and military operations, is deliberately blurred. This obfuscation is achieved by using a wider range of means: violent and non-violent, military and civilian, in a carefully planned manner without unnecessarily crossing the threshold for war and direct conflict, even if the level of escalation varies.

The concept of "hybrid warfare" consists of three phases, and each phase consists of three sub-phases¹⁰⁰:

Preparation phase

The preparation phase is aimed at identifying or discovering, recording and studying the strategic, political, economic, social and infrastructural weaknesses and vulnerabilities of a particular state, as well as setting up and developing the necessary means in order to exploit them to achieve the goals of the "attacker". The means for identifying and studying the indicated weaknesses and vulnerabilities basically include traditional diplomatic and non-diplomatic activities and the activities of "soft - coercion - persuasion", such as the establishment of political cultural societies, the exercise of economic influence, ensuring a significant media presence, support for separatist movements and other anti-government activities. During this phase, there is no open conflict using violent methods, and measures are taken that do not violate the political and legal threshold, which would serve as an indicator to the target state that aggression is imminent.

Attack phase

In this phase, there is an open and organized use of violence. Unmarked, mostly secretly armed units appear, which set up barricades and checkpoints on key communication routes, ostensibly as an expression of certain dissatisfaction and non-fulfilment of the requirements for the appropriately imposed problem. Institutions at the central or local level are blocked in order to prevent their functioning and to prevent the adoption of political decisions that are not in accordance with the "persuasion" of the attackers. At the same time, well-organized, often armed protesters, dressed in civilian clothes, occupy less important local government buildings, media outlets (radio and TV stations, news agencies) and critical elements of the civilian infrastructure. The seizure of

⁹⁸ Milinko S. Vračar, Razmatranje adekvatnog teorijsko-epistemološkog pristupa u istraživanju fenomena hibridnog ratovanja, dostupno na http://www.isi.mod.gov.rs/multimedia/dodaci/69_2017_7_20_vracar_1534761013.pdf

⁹⁹ Fiona Hill, "Hybrid War: The Real Reason Fighting Stopped in Ukraine – for Now," Reuters, February 26, 2015, <http://blogs.reuters.com/great-debate/2015/02/26/hybrid-war-the-real-reason-fighting-stopped-in-ukraine-for-now/>.

¹⁰⁰ Давор М. Милошевић, Перцепција савремених оружаних сукоба као индикатора хибридног концепта рата - модели, превенције и супростављања хибридним претњима, Војно Дело, 6, 2019, стр. 273.

radio and TV stations prevents the broadcasting of information by the central government and enables the broadcasting of their own targeted information/disinformation. The offensive operations are supported by an intensive information operation aimed at paralyzing decision-makers, causing despair, fear and dissatisfaction among citizens with the official government, weakening the possible resistance of local armed forces and police units by weakening their morale. The command system of a particular state is devastated, disrupted and obstructed through electronic interference, sabotage and the placement of disinformation or through the animation of corrupt statesmen. At the same time, the aggressor state constantly denies its own participation in the crisis that has arisen.

Although most actions in this phase are carried out using non-military means, the use of military forces is also significant. Military forces are deployed near the state border and thus cause psychological pressure on citizens and authorities, as an immediate threat of a possible conventional attack. This influences the central government of the attacked state to abandon the possible use of violent methods to suppress demonstrations, riots and prevent the onset of armed rebellion and secession.

Stabilization phase

In order to consolidate the achieved results, the aggressor state takes additional steps, which, presented as a way out of the situation, are positioned as the most appropriate and expedient for calming the situation. Various forms of supposedly democratic processes are organized, such as referendums, declarations, resignations for moral reasons, etc. after which, and if some element does not fit into their plans, there may be specific military-police attacks or the use of informal units as special forces formed for that purpose by the aggressor state. The ultimate political goal of this type of warfare is to prevent the independent existence of the attacked state in that format of social order and with that political and economic capacity. The attacked state is no longer able to conduct an independent foreign policy at a time when it loses territory, population, resources and credibility. Hybrid war is a conceptual departure from the classical theory of armed conflicts and in its conceptual definition contains positions that are found in postmodernist theories of war. The essence of the new observation is that the dominant use of armed force, which means the destruction and annihilation of the enemy, is losing its importance.

The focus of action is on "taking over the enemy" and engaging him in fulfilling one's own interests. This approach is significantly conditioned by globalization, the technological revolution and the general dominance of the neoliberal concept, where the imperative is actually economic interest and market expansion. It has been shown that hybrid warfare includes traditional and non-traditional, i.e. military and non-military ways of waging war, with the expansion of its action into a sphere that is not exclusively military. It is also a new view of such an important social phenomenon as war. Given the wide range of actions that can be used in a hybrid military operation, it is quite certain that non-military forms will initially be given priority over options that involve the direct engagement of military capacities¹⁰¹. Their diversity and flexibility in application indicate the need for constant monitoring and study of this type of action, so that the state can develop the ability to early recognize and quickly find an appropriate response to non-military hybrid threats. It is clear that larger and richer states have an advantage in this, and therefore weaker ones must make greater efforts and demonstrate institutional readiness,

¹⁰¹ Мирослав Митровиќ, „Економски и енергетски аспекти на хибридната закана за националната безбедност“, Воено дело 6/2017, 304-315.

which implies the integration of all state and social capacities, for a correct and timely reaction.¹⁰²

Possible ways of managing the masses, i.e. public opinion, in order to achieve the goals of certain interest groups that can be identified with hybrid action against a certain state, are recognized through:

(1) Influence on the value system and insistence on dominant positions that glorify new "democratic" values in the image of developed Western democracies;

(2) Formation of various groups of like-minded people (civic groups, cultural centres, political parties, non-governmental organizations, etc.) who represent the protagonists of certain values that are common or formulate them as common for the purpose of a controlled appearance in order to emphasize the "difference" in relation to public opinion that supports the current regime and problematizing all those issues on which the "difference" is established;

(3) Strong propaganda activity and increased action through all media forms, constantly emphasizing the difference and deviation from the regime and its supporters, which leads to increased antagonism towards dissenters (clearer establishment of the relations between the old and the new, the undemocratic and the democratic, the backward and the progressive, etc.);

(4) Establishment of "democratic" public opinion as the main driver of political change, based on the demonization of the current regime and the trivialization of the existing value system that created or supports the current regime.

"Colour revolutions", as an element of hybrid war

"Colour revolutions" are also an element of hybrid wars. "Colour revolutions" in fact, represent a type of coup, which is mainly realized with a non-violent type of resistance to the regime, with the active participation of the masses in street demonstrations, with political and financial support from outside¹⁰³.

"Colour revolutions" are essentially special operations of hybrid warfare aimed at carrying out a coup d'état, which are carried out using political, information, communication, sabotage-terrorist and moral-psychological methods of influence in gross violation of international law¹⁰⁴. The goals of such illegal activities can be the complete or partial disintegration of the state, a qualitative change in its internal or foreign policy, the replacement of the state leadership with loyal regimes, the establishment of external

¹⁰² The challenges faced by weaker states, as noted, are further compounded by conditions of systemic, endemic corruption and organized crime. Addressing these challenges requires qualitatively radical, structural reforms within key systems and subsystems, as emphasized by Miodrag Labović in his scholarly study, "Системско владеење на правото против системската корупција и организираниот криминал- Стратешка визија со конкретни реално одржливи и практично спроведливи решенија за нашите најголеми проблеми- Како Македонија може да стане функционална држава"., Култура Скопје, 2024 Integrating insights from this work could provide valuable guidance for designing effective institutional strategies and ensuring timely and comprehensive state responses.

¹⁰³ Милош Р. Миленковиќ*, Мирослав Митровиќ, Обојене револуције у парадигми хибридног рата

¹⁰⁴ Игор Н. Панарин, Хибридни рат, теорија и пракса, Београд 2019 година, стр.325.

control over the state, its criminalization and subordination to the dictates of other states or transnational corporations.¹⁰⁵

This type of revolution most often occurs in such a way that first certain so-called non-governmental organizations and intelligence services in certain countries form political and civil associations and strengthen them to the point where they become strong enough to oppose the legal government¹⁰⁶. Such strength is not valued through the prism of strength expressed through conventional or unconventional capacities and resources, but through the ability to impose opinions, spread disinformation, build awareness of powerlessness, lethargy and hopelessness. Such conditions correspond to the imposition of opinions that the current government is not competent, does not work in the interest of the citizens, but rather the opposite. The conditions of hopelessness and apathy among citizens do not provide an opportunity to identify threats that are imposed. Therefore, most often the people accept such conditions and believe that they will succeed in obtaining positive power and favourable conditions for a normal life.

However, one of the characteristics of "colour revolutions" is that the level of explicit violence is relatively low. That is why today the Internet, social networks and modern electronic devices are used to mobilize the masses. Mass communication, based on modern technologies, is particularly suitable for managing public opinion as the broadest generator of group motivation. The masses, or public opinion, represent a social category prone to management, significantly less stable than the value system and political culture. It can be assumed that certain foreign or domestic factors can raise a certain issue that would raise it high in the focus of public opinion in the countries that are objects of hybrid action, especially those that relate to poverty reduction, "democratization of society", reduction of corruption, etc. In this way, they manage public opinion according to their interests, seducing the group that is the object of action, by inducing or manipulating their attitudes and interests. The processes of managing the motivation and action of the masses are influenced by several factors, and among them they differ and manifest themselves as leaders or creators of public opinion, political events, mass media, personal contacts, group or party indoctrination. By managing the above-mentioned actors and processes, an efficient and targeted reaction of the target population is achieved, in accordance with their dominant public opinion that is created or tense.

The role of modern technologies and social networks available via the Internet has greatly facilitated the preparation, animation of individuals and the organization of protests, starting from mobilizing as many members as possible by distributing pamphlets, ideas and propaganda messages, to developing detailed action plans. In the past, actors of conspiratorial, subversive actions gathered in public buildings or private apartments, in order to avoid identification, but today such "meetings" are mainly organized in the virtual world. In the example of the "colour revolutions", this could look like the widespread social network Facebook, especially among younger people, which is the most common target group in this type of "warfare", and would be used to distribute ideas, recruit members and strive for more massive support for the movement to change the current

¹⁰⁵ Broader consideration about "colored revolutions", their role and practical consequences, see in: Миодраг Лабовиќ, "Системско владеење на правото против системската корупција и организираниот криминал- Стратешка визија со конкретни реално одржливи и практично спроведливи решенија за нашите најголеми проблеми- Како Македонија може да стане функционална држава", Култура Скопје, 2024, стр. 249-259

¹⁰⁶ <http://www.ceopom-istina.rs/politika-i-drustvo/hibridni-rat-tehnologije-protiv-obojenih-revolutsija/?lang=lat>

government. In this way, modern technology and social networks enable easier and faster formation of a movement for reaction and mobilization of citizens. Indeed, their importance and role have been confirmed in practice, in the Arab Spring and the events in Kiev, Ukraine.

Considering the various forms of violent regime change, starting from traditional methods of regime change, to the “colour revolution”, which is considered a more modern action, we can conclude that “colour revolutions” represent the most logical and likely choice for changing the current government in a certain country, implemented as a segment of the hybrid war. There are claims that the “colour revolution”, i.e. the change of government, is actually the last phase of the hybrid war: “In fact, the “colour revolution” is the last phase of the hybrid war, the phase in which the change of government in the country, which is subjected to hybrid aggression, takes place”¹⁰⁷.

If the colour revolutions fail, the next stage follows in which certain victims of such a revolution become rebels or terrorists, and armed intervention begins against such groups. For example, after the failure of the "Arab Spring" in Syria, the fight against terrorism began, with the US and its allies providing open support to certain rebel groups, calling them "moderate rebels", with the aim of overthrowing the then current president Bashar al-Assad¹⁰⁸. The same thing happened with the rebels in Ukraine in the Donbass, who received covert support from Russia.

According to their characteristics, it can be said that colour revolutions are a kind of "hybrids", that is, a combination of a coup d'état and a classic revolution. Just like a coup d'état, there is a change in the holder of state power, without broader social changes (without changes to the state system and the economic and political system), with a certain role of the national army and other bodies from the security and intelligence sphere (this time more passive), as well as with support from an external factor. The similarity with classical revolutions, apart from the name, is also the significant role of citizens in the realization of this type of action.

The name "revolution" is used because it arouses positive feelings and expectations of progressive change. For the success of "colour revolutions", the ability of the main "players" of the coup, the inspirers and organizers is also very important. The constant need for messages and information that are placed in the public, should ideologically, and not only technically, be able to easily reach as many citizens as possible, and success is assessed through the degree of persuasiveness of them to animate and put under control as many people as possible. Of course, colour revolutions do not represent spontaneous animating of citizens, but rather a well-thought-out and planned campaign with clear and well-targeted messages. As in other types of coups, a large number of actors in colour revolutions, primarily street protesters, are not fully aware of their true role in the events taking place, due to the different forms of understanding the messages and the different interests they want to achieve¹⁰⁹. Without taking all this into account, they are used in numbers as evidence of mass anti-government sentiment, and if necessary, in the event of intervention by government security forces, they can also serve as a living wall and protection for the true bearers and leaders of the movement, driven by the euphoria of

¹⁰⁷ See in: Итан Буено де Мескита, Промена на режимот и револуционерни претприемачи, Американски преглед на политички науки, том 104, бр. 3 (август 2010), стр. 446.

¹⁰⁸ Кире Јанев – „Хибридни војни“ – Партизан Проект Тетово, 2021

¹⁰⁹ Милош Р. Миленковић* , Мирослав Митровић, Обојене револуције у парадигми хибридног рата, достапно на: <file:///C:/Users/Kire/Downloads/71-2019-6-17-MilenkovicMitrovic%20.pdf>

the crowd. The factors on which the success of colour revolutions depends can be divided into external and internal. External factors are proportionally equal to the interests at the geopolitical and geostrategic level of perception of the great powers, while internal factors are perceived through the conditions, events and social power of the state, primarily the economic and political power of the state in which the colour revolution takes place¹¹⁰. Internal factors include:

- weakness and small number of forces of the central government;
- corruption;¹¹¹
- pronounced economic inequality and tensions;
- interethnic and interreligious conflicts within the country;
- lack of vision for the future (especially pronounced among young people).

How often these so-called colour revolutions occur can be seen from the claim of the American journalist and publicist Wayne Madsen, who claims that as many as 64 colour revolutions were organized by the United States alone¹¹²¹¹³. Such examples are: the "Rose" Revolution in Georgia, the "Orange Revolution" in Ukraine, the Lebanese "Kedra" Revolution, the "Olive Revolution" in Palestine, the "Tulip Revolution" in Kyrgyzstan, and the list also includes coups in Yugoslavia, Kuwait, Libya, Burma, Tibet, Iran, Egypt, Tunisia, Syria and other countries, and similar revolutions were also predicted in Moldova, Mongolia, Uzbekistan, Ecuador, Bolivia and Belarus.

The most serious consequences were left by the "Euromaidan" colour revolution in Ukraine, with the coup in 2013-14, which was followed in 2014 by an internal civil war between the government and the Russian minority in Ukraine. The demonstrators, "democratically" called "Euromaidan" on one hand, and the opponents of the demonstrators called "Antimaidan".

Protests or Euromaidans in support of the "colourful revolution" in Ukraine were organized in parallel starting on November 24, 2013 by countries such as Poland, Great Britain, Germany, France, Italy, Sweden, Austria, Czech Republic, Bulgaria, the United States and Canada¹¹⁴.

New "colour revolution" followed. In that region, a "colourful revolution" was taking place in Georgia, which failed to overthrow the elected government there. The President of Georgia, Salome Zourabichvili, who is a French citizen and an associate of Zbigniew Brzezinski, an advisor in the American governments of Reagan and Jimmy Carter, and strongly supported by the EU, did not recognize the elected government of the "Georgian Dream" party in 2023 after the elections, and then the presidential elections in 2024, which were won by Mikhail Kavelashvili, and called for protests that took place.

¹¹⁰ Andrew Korybko, Hybrid Wars: The Indirect Adaptive Approach to Regime Change, Peoples Friendship University of Russia, Moscow, 2015, p. 35.

¹¹¹ Miodrag Labovic: Policing in Central and Eastern Europe – Social Control of Unconventional Deviance, Conference Proceedings, Social control of institutional organized crime, 2011, стр. 194, 200, 208 <https://www.ncjrs.gov/pdffiles1/nij/Mesko/235122.pdf>

¹¹² Милош Р. Миленковић* , Мирослав Митровић, Обојене револуције у парадигми хибридног рата, достапно на: <///C:/Users/Kire/Downloads/71-2019-6-17-MilenkovicMitrovic%20.pdf>

¹¹³ Илья Вадимович Максимов, «Цветная» революция – социальный процесс или сетевая технология?, Монография, Москва, 2010, стр. 8.

¹¹⁴ <https://www.blic.rs/vesti/svet/svet/vejn-medsen-amerika-sirom-sveta-organizovala-64-obojene-revolucije-medu-kojima-je-i/stnnqk7>

The first to appear at the protests, as usual, were schoolchildren and students, and then people organized into violent groups and people from other countries appeared.

Unlike Ukraine, there were no armed clashes in Georgia, no paramilitary units formed by the two opposing sides. The European Union, which granted Georgia candidate status for accession in 2023, withdrew its decision, and the new Georgian government, after the protests, decided to freeze its application for EU membership until 2028.

The bloody fist and the bloody hand, the symbol of the coloured (colourful) revolutions, we are seeing up close now in Serbia with the blockades for more than a year, were seen all over the world. The pattern is the same, as with all "colourful revolutions", the last initiative of the Serbian blockaders, after the unsuccessful ten-month demonstrations, blockades and violence, is the public call to act as in Nepal.

In Nepal, the bloody "colour revolution" took over 30 people in 48 hours, half of whom, not in riots, but in public, mass murders of political opponents. Officially, 22 murders and a dozen "disappearances" were reported. During the protests in Bangladesh, on Capitol Hill and during the riots in Kathmandu, it is estimated that it was the work of such colour revolutions. This choreography was also seen in 2003 in Albania, when the non-governmental organization "mjaft!", which translates as enough, launched a campaign against corruption with violence.

The initial cause, the death of 15 people from a canopy collapse at the Novi Sad railway station, is no longer mentioned by anyone. They are demanding a government without elections or elections organized by the blockaders, the secession of Vojvodina and the recognition of Kosovo.

In Portugal, in Lisbon, 21 people recently died from a cable car collapse, but there was no "colour revolution". Portugal is not yet ripe for "democracy".

This form of hybrid action also existed in our country, namely, on May 5, 2016, the so-called "Colourful Revolution" took place. Through the publication of the so-called "bombs" of the largest opposition party, SDSM. A large number of journalists and civic activists were given "folders" with their wiretapped conversations¹¹⁵. The Colourful Revolution took place under the slogan "No Justice, No Peace" and had eight demands:

- withdrawal of the decision to abolish;
- resignation of President Ivanov;
- pronouncement of the Constitutional Court on the constitutionality of the SPO;
- establishment of a special department of the Criminal Court competent for SPO cases;
- withdrawal of the decision to hold parliamentary elections on June 5, 2016;
- participation of independent representatives of civil society in resolving the crisis;
- the crisis to be resolved on the territory of Macedonia; and
- formation of a transitional government that will implement the urgent reform priorities from the Priebe Report.

In the following period, civil protests for the resignation of the Government continued, and with the mediation of the European Union and the United States, political

¹¹⁵ Од Букурешт до Преспа, Сведоштва на едно време Македонија 2008 - 2018, Фондација Отворено општество – Македонија, Скопје, 2020, стр242, достапно на: <https://fosm.mk/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/foom-od-bukurest-do-prespa-mk-za-web.pdf>

talks began to resolve the political crisis and to ensure conditions for fair and democratic elections, which ended with the signing of the Pržino Agreement on June 2 and its annex on July 15. An important feature of the "colourful" protests was the absence of any party symbols, but also the presence of tens of thousands of independent citizens and members of various opposition parties. Over time, some protesters became visible and recognizable faces of the resistance, but it had no leader. The operation was conducted in 4 phases¹¹⁶:

- creation of a crisis and destabilization of the state;
- compromising the government and institutions;
- change of government and bringing in a new one;
- realization of the set goals.

All the facts support the thesis that the "colour revolution" and the events of April 27, 2017 are the result of a hybrid war¹¹⁷.

"Colour revolutions" or insurgency

We have examined the basis of the "coloured" or "colourful" revolutions. Due to their development into a possible direct conflict expressed with the use of conventional weapons, it is necessary to make a distinction from insurgency or to show where "coloured" revolutions merge or distance themselves from insurgency. Insurgency is presented as a set of activities of an organized, often ideologically motivated group or movement, which aims to cause or prevent political change by the ruling authorities, focusing on persuading and intimidating the population using violence or subversion. Insurgency uses violent and non-violent tactics to achieve the goals of the organization that "rebelled". Nonviolent tactics are used to achieve political goals without the use of force. Violent tactics are usually used in combination with nonviolent tactics. Using a combination of these two tactics, supported by propaganda, helps recruit new fighters, as well as gain popular support. Insurgency is inherently an asymmetric threat. Asymmetric warfare is a conflict in which a weaker adversary uses unusual surprise tactics to attack the weak points of a stronger adversary. Such tactics include: terrorism, guerrilla warfare, criminal activities, subversion or propaganda¹¹⁸. Violent tactics of insurgency include: terrorism, guerrilla warfare, sabotage, or conventional operations. Rebels often use terrorism and guerrilla warfare as tactics to achieve their goals, because they do not have the ability to oppose the government or counterinsurgency forces with conventional operations. Subversion and propaganda are the two most common forms of nonviolent struggle. Terrorism, due to the diversity of forms and methods that can be used, is an acceptable tool for action of the insurgent group, which independently chooses the goals of action, makes decisive plans and uses maximum conspiratoriality to realize the tasks¹¹⁹. Later, in order to cause fear, unrest, panic, distrust in the institutions of the system, publicly through the media, they take responsibility for the event and thereby identify themselves in the public, often with a clear interpretation of the goals and demands, and also advertise themselves for the effect of possible massification and expansion of their ranks through quality and gradual selection.

¹¹⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=liSc995tSQM&feature=youtu.be>

¹¹⁷ Нормално конкретни докази за инволвираност тешко дека ќе може да се пронајдат, ниту пак посочените држави би го признале евентуалното учество во овие настани, нешто што е карактеристично токму за хибридните војни

¹¹⁸ FM 3-24.2, Tactics in counterinsurgency, Headquarters Department of the Army, Washington, DC, 2009, p. 2-20.

¹¹⁹ З. Димовски, Тероризам, Графотранс, Скопје, 2007

A common denominator for most rebel groups is their goal of gaining control over the population or a certain territory, including its resources. This goal distinguishes rebel groups from terrorist organizations. According to Bard O'Neill, insurgency is probably the most widespread type of armed conflict since the creation of organized political communities. He defines insurgency as "a comprehensive concept that refers to a conflict between a government and a group or opponent that uses both political resources and violence to change, reformulate, or adhere to the legitimacy of one or more of four key aspects of politics". The four key aspects are¹²⁰:

- integrity of the borders and composition of the nation-state;
- the political system;
- the government;
- the policies that determine who gets what in society.

A very important segment for politicians and security agencies in preventing insurgency is the concept of incipient insurgency. The concept of incipient insurgency covers the period before the insurgency and the organizational phases of the insurgent conflict¹²¹. It refers to situations in which subversive activity by an undeveloped insurgent group is only a potential threat to governments where anti-government incidents occur frequently, where the organization is recognizable to the public, and its activities in the future can be recognized and predicted. A revolutionary group that aims to become an insurgent must, at a minimum, aim to build the organization, carry out selection and recruitment, train people, obtain material and other values, present its beliefs and goals, etc. The group may also choose to incite riots or work stoppages, infiltrate the legitimate political apparatus, and engage in terrorism as a means of promotion. If more than one of these signs is present and their magnitude is high, it can be concluded that the group has engaged in these activities and poses a more serious threat. These are classified as preparatory activities. The most alarming signs – those that will almost certainly signal the beginning of a serious insurgency threat – include significant foreign aid, either from governments or from other insurgent or extremist groups, receiving guerrilla training, acquiring large amounts of resources for carrying out actions, and creating an organization that is most often composed of two wings: a political and a conspiratorial military wing. The difference with "coloured" revolutions is obvious, and especially concerns the inspirers, the members of the group, the way of "working", intergroup relations and the way of communicating with the people, plans, goals, and methods of action. According to these characteristics, insurgency stands out as a special way of acting, although the goals are identical to the emergence of "coloured" revolutions, but it represents support for certain initiatives and the achievement of an appropriate goal.

¹²⁰ Aaron M Young, David H. Gray, *Insurgency, Guerilla Warfare and Terrorism: Conflict and its Application for the Future*, стр.2, достапно на:
<http://globalsecuritystudies.com/Young%20Insurgency%20FINAL.pdf>

¹²¹ Кире Јанев- „Хибридни војни„-Партизан Проект Тетово, 2021

CONCLUSION

From the above, we can conclude that "colour revolutions" and according to the content of the measures and goals represent a hybrid form of action. They actually represent a type of coup d'état that is carried out mainly through "non-violent" resistance to the current government, with the active participation of groups of citizens through street demonstrations, but also with political and financial support from outside from other states, institutions, terrorist organizations. According to their characteristics, "colour revolutions" can be said to be a type of "hybrid" or a combination of a coup d'état and a classic revolution. Given that "colour revolutions" emphasize the importance of citizen participation as one of the dominant actors, they are essentially reduced to a measure of populist dominance. However, their success does not depend on that and whether the majority of the population in a country or city actively supports the idea of a "color revolution", but rather the fact that the inspirers and organizers of mass protests gather a sufficiently large number of people who, with their actions, messages and activities, pose a security challenge to the government. The size depends on each individual country, on the characteristics of its leadership, the economic and political strength of the government and the ability of its security apparatus (police, army, judiciary) to face these types of security risks. Social dominance is achieved at the moment when this "critical mass", which has risen to overthrow the current government, expects an inadequate and "chaotic" reaction from the government. After that, the initiative is on the side of the protesters, who, with active help from abroad, more easily manage to bring about a change of government. The ability of coup supporters, instigators and organizers to convey certain messages and information to the public and for them to easily reach as many citizens as possible, ideologically and not just technically, is extremely important for the success of "colour revolutions". In creating and managing information, all the knowledge and skills of propaganda and public relations are used, supported by the Internet and modern means of communication. "Colour revolutions" are therefore not spontaneous gatherings of citizens, but a well-thought-out and planned campaign with clear and very focused messages. As with many types of coups, a large number of actors in "colour revolutions", primarily street demonstrators, are not fully aware of their true role in the events taking place. Regardless, they are used as evidence of mass anti-government sentiment, and if necessary, in the event of intervention by government security forces, they can also serve as a "human wall" and protection for the true bearers and leaders of the movement.

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